

City of Toronto (CMA) Highlights

Population
= 6,202,225

Number of Homes
= 2,394,205

Population Density
= 1,051/Km²

5-year Population change = 4.6%

Age Distribution by Gender

Age 55+

29%

Age 25-54

43%

Age 0-24

28%

\$47,600
Average Income
(after-tax)

Income & Employment

Prevalence of Low-income by Age (%)

13.3%
Unemployment
Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

84.7%

Immigrants

46.6%

Recent Immigrants

6.4%

Recent Immigrants by Birthplace

Immigrants by Birthplace

Language Spoken at Home

Punjabi

Mandarin

Spanish

Urdu

Tamil

Cantonese

English | 65.5%

Non-official Languages | 26.3%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

- No certificate, diploma or degree
- Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
- Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

\$2,108_(own)

\$1,618_(rent)

Average monthly shelter costs

35%

Rent their home

\$1,112,000

Average home value

31%

Apartment ≥ 5 stories

43%

Built before 1980

5%

Major repair needed

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Siddiqui, S., Orr, E., Ganann, R. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team. (2023). Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile-Toronto.

URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Data Source: Statistics Canada. 2021. *Toronto CMA*. www.statcan.gc.ca

Institute for Research on Aging

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Public Health Agency of Canada

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